

I. Ph.D Registration Fee under internal Research Supervisor: (from 01-08-2011)

S.No	Name of the Item	Ph.D - Part Time/Full-Time			
		University Departments		Affiliated Colleges	
		Arts	Science	Arts	Science
1.	Registration Application fee	#500	#500	#500	#500
2.	Special Fees	1000	1000	*1000	*1000
3.	Thesis evaluation	4000	4000	4000	4000
4.	Synopsis submission	1500	1500	1500	1500
5.	Library Fees	500	500	500	500
6.	Development of infrastructural facilities in the University/College	1500	1500	1500	1500
7.	Registration Fees	#2000	#2000	#2000	#2000
8.	Provisional and Degree certificate	1000	1000	1000	1000
9.	Tuition Fees	#2500	#2500	##2500	##2500
10.	Students welfare fund	50	50	50	50
11.	Admission fee	50	50	50	50
12.	Internet/Bar coded identify card/Calender/Magzine	300	300	300	300
13.	Special lab fees for computers	500	500	*500	*500
14.	Special lab fees for chemicals/ handling equipments	-----	500	-----	*500
15.	Doctoral Committee meeting fee	3000	3000	3000	3000
	TOTAL Ist year (one time payment)	18,400	18,900	18,400	18,900

Out of one time payment (Rs.18,400/18,900), fees to be paid by the candidate to the college concerned

Arts : Rs.4,000/-*
Science : Rs.4,500/-*

Fees to be paid by the candidate to the Periyar University

Arts : Rs.14,400/-
Science : Rs.14,400/-

In addition to one time payment mentioned above, the candidates have to pay subsequent yearly fees prescribed below:

S.No.	Particulars	Arts	Science
1.	Library Fee	500/-	500/-
2.	Infrastructure Fee	500/-	1000/-
3.	Tuition Fee	##2500/-	##2500/-
4.	Lab fee for chemicals/handling equipments	-Nil-	*500/-
5.	Lab fee for computer	*500/-	*500/-
	Total	4000/-	5000/-

In the subsequent year fee (Rs.4000 / Rs.5000), those who are registered in the department of affiliated college, following fees to be paid by the candidate

To the University

	Arts	Science
1.Library fee	Rs. 500/-	Rs. 500/-
2.Infrastructure fee	Rs. 500/-	Rs.1000/-
Total:	Rs. 1000/-	Rs.1500/-

To the College Concerned

1.Tuition fee	Rs. 2500/-#	Rs.2500/-#
2.Lab fee for computer	Rs. 500/-	Rs. 500/-
3.Lab fee for chemical /handling equip.	-----	Rs. 500/-
Total:	Rs. 3000/-	Rs.3500/-

II. Other fees for Ph.D Research Programme:

1. Change of Topic	Rs. 500/-
2. Course Work fee (Per course Rs.300X3)	Rs. 900/-
3. Late submission of Thesis for 1 st 6 Month	Rs.2000/-
4. Exam fees (per course as per PG examination)	Rs. 150/-
5. Recognition application form for Ph.D registration	Rs. 50/-

III. Ph.D-Registration Fee under external Research Supervisor

1. Fees under External guideship	
a) One time fee	Rs. 20,000/-
b) Subsequent year	Rs. 10,000/-

- Note:**
- For SC/ST candidate's #Registration Application fee, #Tuition fee and #Registration fee are exempted.
 - For availing fee exemption, the SC/ST student has to submit the attested copy of community certificate along with the Registration

Ph.D Programme

S.No	Name of the College	Subject	Ph.D Programme offered
1.	Govt. Arts College(Autonomous), Salem.7	Tamil English Chemistry Geology History Statistics	Both Both PT Both Both Both
2.	Govt. Arts College for Men, Krishnagiri.	Tamil	Both
3.	Govt. Arts College, Dharmapuri.	Commerce	Part-time
4.	Aringar Anna Government Arts College Namakkal.	Tamil	Both
5.	Sri Sarada College for women, Salem	History Economics Chemistry Mathematics English Commerce	Both Both Both Both Both Both
6.	JKK. Nataraja College of Arts & Science Komarapalayam.	Zoology	Part-time
7.	Kandaswami Kandar's College, P. Velur, Namakkal Dist.	Mathematics Economics Commerce Chemistry	Part-time Part-time Both Both
8.	Salem Sowdeswari College, Salem-10	Commerce Statistics	Part-time Both
9.	Mahendra Arts & Science College, kalipatti, Namakkal.Dt.	Tamil	Both
10.	KSR College of Arts & Science, Tiruchengode.	Microbiology Biotechnology Business Administration	Both Both Both
11.	MGR College, Hosur	Tamil Microbiology	Both Both
12.	Muthayammal Arts & Science College Rasipuram	Biochemistry Microbiology	Both Both
13.	Vivekanandha college of Arts & Science for women, Elalyampalayam, Tiruchengode	Microbiology Biotechnology	Full-time Full-time
14.	PGP College of Arts & Science, Namakkal.	Tamil	Both
15.	Selvam Arts & Science College Namakkal	Biotechnology	Both
16.	Regional Sericulture Research Station, Salem	Botany & Sericulture	Part-time
17.	Biomedical Engineering Research Foundation, Kupponoor, Salem 636 122	Biotechnology	Both